

Post-harvest Changes in the Status of Nitrogen and Organic Carbon in Soil Treated with Fertilizers and Pesticides for Growing *Raphanus sativus*

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$\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ was found maximum in soils supplied with fertilizers only (C_f) and pesticides were found to inhibit the production and maintenance of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ in soils. Fertilizers and pesticides showed increased percentage of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ than the original level (OL), although natural soil showed more $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ than the treated soils. In presence of metasytox there was an increase in $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ percentage than the fertilizer (C_f) and carbofuran treated (P) soils. Rate of nitrification was inhibited by the presence of fertilizers and pesticides. However, pesticides increased the rate of nitrification in the soils than fertilizers only. Organic carbon percentage was found to be maximum in the original level. Pesticide treated soils had a higher organic carbon level than the fertilizers treated soil.

IN modern farming uses of fertilizers and pesticides are increasing for the improvement of agricultural production. However, the addition of these chemicals cause changes in chemical and biological processes.

The effect of different fertilizers on the nitrogen and carbon cycles in the soil has been worked out^{1,2,3}. Inhibition of nitrification⁴⁻⁶, enhancement in N-fixation and nitrification⁷, unaffected nitrification⁸, nitrate accumulation⁹, decline of nitrate level¹⁰ and an enhancement in ammonical nitrogen and decline in nitrate nitrogen¹¹ in soil supplied with aldicarb¹¹ have been reported as resulting from the application of insecticides/pesticides.

Effect of pesticides on soil organic matter is not well understood, although there are reports on decline in the organic carbon level of soil¹², and adsorption of pesticides by organic matter¹³.

In the present work an attempt has, therefore, been made to study these effects in detail.

Experimental

5 kg soil was taken in earthen pots and five seeds of radish (*Raphanus sativus*) were sown in each pot. One set of pots was supplied with inorganic and organic nitrogenous fertilizers alone and in combination with P and K, (C_f) at the rate of 50 : 50 : 100 kg/ha. Another set of pots was supplied with the same fertilizers and carbamate insecticide (P_o) at the rate of 17.67 kg/ha. The third set of pots was supplied with fertilizers and organophosphorus insecticide (P_m) at the rate of 400 ml in 197.68 gallon/ha. Inorganic fertilizers used were ammonium sulphate (N) alone and in combination with superphosphate (P_2O_5) and muriate of potash (K_2O). Organic fertilizers used were urea (U) alone, urea in combination with

inorganic P and K and cowdung manure (CM) alone. Carbamate and organophosphorus insecticides were carbofuran and metasytox, respectively.

Estimation of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ and organic carbon: For the estimation of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ and $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ the reported method of De¹⁴ was used. Organic carbon of the soil was done by chromic acid colorimetric method of Dutta *et al*¹⁵ and percentage of organic matter was calculated by multiplying the percentage of organic carbon with 1.724. The whole experiment was done in three replicates.

Results and Discussion

From the data presented in Tables 1(a), (b) and (c), it is clear that in presence of carbofuran there was more nitrate utilization by radish than in presence of fertilizers or metasytox, although the rate of nitrification was greater in presence of metasytox than carbofuran. It is quite clear that metasytox, being a sulphur containing compound, could not be broken down microbiologically so easily on the surface of the leaves and probably choked the absorbing cells of radish leaves, thereby hampering CO_2 assimilation and synthesis of glucose. Due to this adverse effect in the process of photosynthesis, the metabolic activities within the plant leaves swayed in a fashion that affected nitrate absorption/utilization for the synthesis of protein and other nitrogenous compounds. This was probably not the case with carbofuran, whose metabolic pathway in plants, insects and mammals was known to show the formation and absorption of additional energy material (O-glucose) resulting in more utilization and absorption of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$. In spite of this result with respect to carbofuran, the residual soil treated with this insecticide showed more $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$. This seems to be a microbial effect in the soil in which the additional glucose as a result of

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TABLE 1(a)—POST-HARVEST CHANGES IN THE STATUS OF NH₃-N, NO₃-N, NO₃/NH₃ AND ORGANIC CARBON IN SOIL TREATED WITH FERTILIZERS AND PESTICIDES FOR GROWING *Raphanus sativus*

Changes in NH₃-N, NO₃-N, NO₃/NH₃ and organic carbon in soil.

Treatment	C _f			Organic carbon matter		P _m					P _o				
	NH ₃ -N %	NO ₃ -N %	NO ₃ /NH ₃	%	%	NH ₃ -N %	NO ₃ -N %	NO ₃ /NH ₃	Organic carbon %	Organic carbon %	NH ₃ -N %	NO ₃ -N %	NO ₃ /NH ₃	Organic carbon %	Organic carbon %
Control	0.0084	0.0070	0.83	0.78	1.34	0.0042	0.0056	1.33	0.84	1.45	0.0070	0.0070	1.00	0.86	1.48
N	0.0070	0.0056	0.80	0.86	1.48	0.0070	0.0070	1.00	0.92	1.59	0.0056	0.0056	1.00	1.13	1.95
NPK	0.0070	0.0070	1.00	1.39	2.40	0.0070	0.0084	1.20	1.05	1.81	0.0070	0.0070	1.00	1.30	2.24
U	0.0070	0.0056	0.80	1.32	2.28	0.0084	0.0070	0.83	1.34	2.31	0.0084	0.0056	0.67	1.53	2.64
UPK	0.0070	0.0070	1.00	1.30	2.24	0.0070	0.0056	0.80	1.15	1.98	0.0084	0.0070	0.83	1.20	2.07
CM	0.0070	0.0070	1.00	1.53	2.64	0.0070	0.0084	1.20	2.02	3.48	0.0056	0.0056	1.00	1.36	2.35
Original level (OL)	0.0063	0.0091	1.44	1.41	2.43										

	NH ₃ -N	NO ₃ -N	NO ₃ /NH ₃	Organic carbon
C.D. at 5%				
Fertilizer treatment	NS	0.0007*	NS	0.0675*
Pesticide	NS	0.0005*	NS	NS
Interaction	0.0028*	0.0012*	NS	0.1172*

* Significant

TABLE 1(b)—EFFICIENCY ORDER OF THE CHANGES SHOWN UNDER TABLE 1(a)

Factors	C _f	P _m	P _o
NH ₃ -N	Cont. > N - NPK - U - UPK - CM > OL	U > N - NPK - UPK - CM > OL > Cont.	U - UPK > Cont. - NPK > OL > N - CM
NO ₃ -N	OL > Cont. - NPK - UPK - CM > N - U	OL > NPK - CM > N = U > Cont. - UPK	OL > Cont. - NPK - UPK > N - U - CM
NO ₃ /NH ₃	OL > NPK - UPK - CM > Cont. > N = U	OL > Cont. > NPK = CM > N > U > UPK	OL > Cont. - N - NPK - CM > UPK > U
Organic carbon	CM > OL > NPK > U > UPK > N > Cont.	CM > OL > U > UPK > NPK > N > Cont.	U > OL > CM > NPK > UPK > N > Cont.

TABLE 1(c)—GENERAL EFFICIENCY ORDER OF THE CHANGES SHOWN UNDER TABLE 1(a)

Factors	NH ₃ -N	NO ₃ -N	NO ₃ /NH ₃	Organic carbon
Pesticide	C _f > P _o > P _m > OL	OL > P _m > C _f > P _o	OL > P _m > P _o > C _f	OL > P _o > P _m > C _f
Fertilizers	U > UPK > NPK > Cont. - N - CM > OL	OL > NPK > CM > Cont. = UPK > N - U	OL > NPK - CM > Cont. > N > UPK > U	CM > OL > U > NPK > UPK > N > Cont.
Interaction	Cont(C _f) - U(P _m) = U(P _o) - UPK(P _o)	NPK(P _m) - CM(P _m) > Cont(C _f) - NPK(C _f) - UPK(C _f) - CM(C _f) - Cont(P _o) - UPK(P _o) - CM(P _o)	Cont(P _m) > NPK(C _f) - UPK(C _f) - CM(C _f) - Cont(P _o) - N(P _o) - NPK(P _o) - CM(P _o)	CM(P _m) > CM(C _f) > U(P _o)

OL - Natural soil ; C_f - Fertilizer treated soil
P_m - Fertilizer treated soil with metasytox
P_o - Fertilizer treated soil with carbofuran

carbofuran addition enhanced the formation of NH₃-N either by nitrogen fixation or by rapid decomposition of root residues to maintain a proper C/N ratio in the soil.

Since there was more nitrate absorption in presence of metasytox, the nitrogen content of the soil became less and to maintain a proper C/N ratio more carbon was lost from the soil to the atmosphere. Carbofuran applied soils thus recorded more organic carbon content than soils in which the plants were grown in presence of metasytox.

The status of different forms of nitrogen in the original soil and soils treated with fertilizers only, did not show a fixed tendency of nitrogen utilization/absorption although in general it appears that there was more ammonification and nitrification in the soils treated with the fertilizers. Under such a trend there would be more organic carbon content in comparison to the other treatments of pesticides which was not the case. In the original level of the soil, different forms of nitrogen and organic carbon, barring NH₃-N, NO₃-N, nitrification and

organic carbon were the highest in comparison to the other treatments.

Regarding interaction between fertilizers and the two pesticides it appears that the efficiency order of the soil in relation to the $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ content treated with U and metasystox was the same as the control where no fertilizer was added. So was the case with the soil where U and UPK both were applied with carbofuran. The maximum efficiency order in relation to the $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ or nitrification was found in the soils treated with NPK and CM in combination with metasystox. Rate of nitrification was increased by the application of metasystox only than other treatments. However, as regards the interaction in relation to the organic carbon content of the soil it appeared that the soils treated with cowdung manure and metasystox is at the highest value followed by cowdung manure only and then urea treated with carbofuran.

It has been observed that for maximum $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ content, interaction between fertilizer treatments and pesticides was significant statistically at 5% [Table 1(a)]. For $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, fertilizer treatments, pesticides and their interaction with each other were statistically significant. For percentage of organic carbon,

fertilizer treatment and its interaction with pesticides were also significant statistically.

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